

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE METHODS OF SOLVING NON-LINEAR PROGRAMMING PROBLEM

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Abstract: The work present in this paper is based on a comparative study of the methods of solving Non-linear programming (NLP) problem. We know that Kuhn-Tucker condition method is an efficient method of solving Non-linear programming problem. By using Kuhn-Tucker conditions the quadratic programming (QP) problem reduced to form of Linear programming(LP) problem, so practically simplex type algorithm can be used to solve the quadratic programming problem (Wolfe's Algorithm). We have arranged the materials of this paper in following way. First we discuss about non-linear programming problems. In second step we discuss Kuhn- Tucker condition method of solving NLP problems. Finally we compare the solution obtained by Kuhn- Tucker condition method with other methods. For problem so consider we use MATLAB programming to graph the constraints for obtaining feasible region. Also we plot the objective functions for determining optimum points and compare the solution thus obtained with exact solutions.

Keywords: Non-linear programming, objective function ,convex-region, pivotal element, optimal solution.

1 Introduction

For decision making optimization plays the central role. Optimization is the synonym of the word maximization/minimization. It means choose the best. In our time to take any decision, we use most modern scientific methods best on computer implementations. Modern optimization theory based on computing and we can select the best alternative value of the objective function. The optimization problems have two major divisions. One is linear programming problem and other is non-linear programming problem [1]. But the modern game theory, dynamic programming problem, integer programming problem also part of the optimization theory having wide range of application in modern science, economics

and management. Linear and non-linear programming problem optimizes an objective function subject to a class of linear and non-linear equality or inequality conditions called constraints, usually subject to non-negativity restrictions of the variables. It was introduced by [2]. In the present work we tried to compare some methods of non-linear programming problem. We know that, for solving a non-linear programming problem various algorithms can be used, but only few of the methods will be affective for solving problems. Usually none of the algorithms have no relations with others and there is no universal algorithm like simplex method in linear programming for solving a non-linear programming problem. In the work we will apply the methods for solving problem rather than its theoretical descriptions.

2 Non-linear programming

Like linear programming, non-linear programming is a mathematical technique for determining the optimal solutions to many business problems. The problem of maximizing or minimizing a given function

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} Z = f(\underline{x}) \\ \text{Subject to} \\ g_i(\underline{x}) \leq b_i \text{ (} \geq b_i \text{)} \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

is called to general non-linear programming problem, if the objective function *i.e.* the function $f(\underline{x})$ or any one of the constraints

function $g_i(\underline{x})$ is non-linear ; or both are non-linear for $\underline{x}$ nonnegative. In a word, the

non-linear programming problem is that of choosing nonnegative values of certain variables, so as to maximize or minimize a given non-linear function subject to a given set of linear or non-linear inequality constraints; or maximize or minimize a linear

Equations (6) through (12) represent a set of necessary conditions which $[x_o, \lambda_o]$ must satisfy if $F(x, \lambda)$ has a saddle point at $[x_o, \lambda_o]$ for $[x, \lambda] \in W$, provided that $F \in c'$.

Now the sufficient conditions can be stated as follows. Let $[x_o, \lambda_o]$ be a point satisfying (6) through (12). Then if there exists an ϵ -neighborhood about $[x_o, \lambda_o]$ such that for points $[x, \lambda_o] \in W$, in this neighborhood $F(x, \lambda_o) \leq F(x_o, \lambda_o) + \nabla_x F(x_o, \lambda_o)(x - x_o)$ (13)
 $F(x_o, \lambda) \geq F(x_o, \lambda_o) + \nabla_\lambda F(x_o, \lambda_o)(\lambda - \lambda_o)$ (14)
 then $F(x, \lambda)$ has a saddle point at $[x_o, \lambda_o]$ for $[x, \lambda] \in W$. If (13) and (14) hold for all $x \in W_1, \lambda \in W_2$, it follows that has a global saddle point at $[x_o, \lambda_o]$ for $[x, \lambda] \in W$.

From the above we can deduce Kuhn-Tucker's conditions as follows:

Let us consider the non-linear programming problem as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Maximize } Z &= f(x) \\ \text{subject to } g(x) &\leq b \\ x &\geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

To obtain Kuhn-Tucker necessary conditions, let us convert the inequality constrains of the above problem to equality constraints by adding a vector of m slack (surplus) variables:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max } Z &= f(x) \\ \text{subject to } g(x) + s &= b \\ \text{or } s &= b - g(x) \text{ where } s^T = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m). \end{aligned}$$

Now the Lagrangian function for the problem takes the form, $L(x, \lambda) = f(x) + \lambda\{b - g(x)\}$

Assumed that $f, g \in c'$, first order necessary conditions can be obtained by taking first order derivatives with respect to x, λ of the Lagrangian function

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} &\equiv \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - \lambda \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} \leq 0 \\ \therefore \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} x &\equiv \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} \right) x = 0 \\ \text{and } \frac{\partial F}{\partial \lambda} &\equiv b - g(x) \geq 0 \\ \therefore \lambda \frac{\partial F}{\partial \lambda} &\equiv \lambda(b - g(x)) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Rewriting the Lagrangian form we get

$$F(x, \lambda) \equiv f(x) + \sum_i \lambda_i (b_i - g_i(x)), \quad i = 1, \dots, m.$$

Now if $f(x)$ takes constraints local optimum at $x = x^*$ it is necessary that a vector λ^* exists such that

$$\begin{aligned} 1. \nabla_x F(x^*, \lambda^*) &\equiv \nabla_x (f(x^*)) - \sum_i \lambda_i^* \nabla_x g_i(x^*) \leq 0 \\ 2. [\nabla_x F(x^*, \lambda^*)]^T x^* &\equiv \sum_{j=1}^n [\nabla_x (f(x^*)) \\ &\quad - \sum_i \lambda_i^* \nabla_x g_i(x^*)] x_j^* = 0 \\ 3. \nabla_\lambda F(x^*, \lambda^*) &\equiv b_i - g_i(x^*) \geq 0 \text{ if } g_i(x^*) \leq b_i \\ &\equiv b_i - g_i(x^*) \leq 0 \text{ if } g_i(x^*) \geq b_i \\ &\equiv b_i - g_i(x^*) = 0 \text{ if } g_i(x^*) = b_i \\ 4. [\nabla_\lambda F(x^*, \lambda^*)] \lambda^* &\equiv \sum_i [b_i - g_i(x^*)] \lambda_i^* = 0. \end{aligned}$$

4 Comparison of solutions by Kuhn-Tucker condition and others

In this part we want to show that various NLP problems can be solved by different methods. Our aim is to show the affective ness of the methods considered:

Example: Let us consider the problem

$$\text{Maximize } Z = 2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2$$

Subject to the constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 + 2x_2 &\leq 4 \\ x_1, x_2 &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

First we want to solve above problem by graphical solution method.

The given problem can be rewriting as:

$$\text{Maximize } Z = -(x_1 - 1)^2 + 3 \left(x_2 + \frac{1}{3} \right)$$

Subject to the constraints

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 + 2x_2 &\leq 4 \\ x_1, x_2 &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that our objective function is a parabola with vertex at (1, -1/3) and constraints are linear. To solve the problem graphically, first we construct the graph of the constraint in the first quadrant since $x_1 \geq 0$ and $x_2 \geq 0$ by considering the inequation to equation. $x_1 + 2x_2 = 4$

and it was introduced by [6].

Each point has co-ordinates of the tupe (x_1, x_2)

and conversely every ordered pair (x_1, x_2) or real numbers determines a point in the plane. Thus our search for the number pair

(x_1, x_2) is restricted to the points of the first quadrant only

Fig.1 Optimum solution by graphical method

We get the convex region OAB as opportunity set. Since our search is for such a pair (x_1, x_2) which gives a maximum value of $2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2$ and lies in the convex region. The desire point will be that point of the region at which a side of the convex region is tangent to the parabola. For this proceed as follows:

Differentiating the equation of the parabola, we get

$$2dx_1 + 3dx_2 - 2x_1dx_1 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{dx_2}{dx_1} = -\frac{2-2x_1}{3} \quad (15)$$

Now differentiating the equation of the constraint, we get

$$dx_1 + 2dx_2 = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{dx_2}{dx_1} = -\frac{1}{2} \quad (16)$$

Solving equation (15) and (16), we get

$$x_1 = \frac{1}{4} \text{ and } x_2 = \frac{15}{8}. \text{ This shows that the}$$

parabola $z = -(x_1 - 1)^2 + 3\left(x_2 + \frac{1}{3}\right)$ has a tangent to it the line $x_1 + 2x_2 = 4$ at the point $\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{15}{8}\right)$. Hence we get the maximum value of the objective function at this point. Therefore,

$$Z_{\max} = 2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2$$

$$= \frac{97}{16} \text{ at } x_1 = \frac{1}{4}, x_2 = \frac{15}{8}.$$

Let us solve the above problem by using [7] Kuhn-Tucker Conditions. The Lagrangian function of the given problem is

$$F(x_1, x_2, \lambda) \equiv 2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2 + \lambda(4 - x_1 - 2x_2).$$

By Kuhn-Tucker conditions, we obtain

- (a) $\frac{\partial F}{\partial x_1} \equiv 2 - 2x_1 - \lambda \leq 0, \quad \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_2} \equiv 3 - 2\lambda \leq 0$
- (b) $\frac{\partial F}{\partial \lambda} \equiv 4 - x_1 - 2x_2 \geq 0$
- (c) $x_1 \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_1} + x_2 \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_2} \equiv x_1(2 - 2x_1 - \lambda) + x_2(3 - 2\lambda) = 0$
- (d) $\lambda \frac{\partial F}{\partial \lambda} \equiv \lambda(4 - x_1 - 2x_2) = 0 \text{ with } \lambda \geq 0.$

Now there arise the following cases:

Case (i) : Let $\lambda = 0$, in this case we get from

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial x_1} \equiv 2 - 2x_1 \leq 0 \text{ and } \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_2} \equiv 3 - 2 \cdot 0 \leq 0$$

$\Rightarrow 3 \leq 0$ which is impossible and this solution is to be discarded and it was introduced by [8].

Case (ii): Let $\lambda \neq 0$. In this case we get from

$$\lambda(4 - x_1 - 2x_2) = 0$$

$$4 - x_1 - 2x_2 = 0 \Rightarrow x_1 + 2x_2 = 4 \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Also from } \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_1} \equiv 2 - 2x_1 - \lambda \leq 0$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial x_2} \equiv 3 - 2\lambda \leq 0 \therefore 2x_1 + \lambda - 2 \geq 0$$

$$\text{and } 2\lambda - 3 \geq 0 \Rightarrow \lambda \geq \frac{3}{2}$$

If we take $\lambda = \frac{3}{2}$, then $2x_1 \geq \frac{1}{2}$

If we consider $2x_1 = \frac{1}{2}$ then $x_1 = \frac{1}{4}$.

Now putting the value of x_1 in (4.3),

$$\text{we get } x_2 = \frac{15}{8}$$

$$\therefore (x_1, x_2, \lambda) = \left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{15}{8}, \frac{3}{2}\right) \text{ for this solution}$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial x_1} \equiv 2 - 2 \cdot \frac{1}{4} - \frac{3}{2} = \frac{4 - 1 - 3}{2} = 0 \text{ satisfied}$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial x_2} \equiv 3 - 2 \cdot \frac{3}{2} = 0 \text{ satisfied}$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \lambda} \equiv 4 - \frac{1}{4} - 2 \cdot \frac{15}{8} = \frac{16 - 1 - 15}{4} = 0 \text{ satisfied}$$

$$x_1 \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_1} + x_2 \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_2} \equiv \frac{1}{4} \times 0 + \frac{15}{8} \times 0 = 0 \text{ satisfied}$$

$$\lambda \frac{\partial F}{\partial \lambda} \equiv \frac{3}{2} \cdot 0 = 0 \text{ satisfied}$$

Thus all the Kuhn-Tucker necessary conditions are satisfied at the point $\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{15}{8}\right)$.

Hence the optimum (maximum) solution to the given NLP problem is

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{\max} &= 2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2 \\ &= 2 \cdot \frac{1}{4} + 3 \cdot \frac{15}{8} - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2 \\ &= \frac{97}{16} \quad \text{at } x_1 = \frac{1}{4}, x_2 = \frac{15}{8}. \end{aligned}$$

Let us solve the problem by Beale's method.

$$\text{Maximize } f(x) = 2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2$$

Subject to the constraints:

$$x_1 + 2x_2 \leq 4$$

$$x_1, x_2 \geq 0$$

Introducing a slack variables s , the constraint becomes

$$x_1 + 2x_2 + s = 4$$

$$x_1, x_2 \geq 0$$

since there is only one constraint, let s be a basic variable. Thus we have by [9]

$$x_B = (s), x_{NB} = (x_1, x_2) \quad \text{with } s = 4$$

Expressing the basic x_B and the objective function in terms of non-basic x_{NB} , we have $s = 4 - x_1 - 2x_2$ and $f = 2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2$.

We evaluated the partial derivatives of f w.r.to non-basic variables at $x_{NB}=0$, we get

$$\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1}\right)_{x_{NB}=0} = (2 - 2x_1)_{x_{NB}=0} = 2 - 2 \cdot 0 = 2$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2}\right)_{x_{NB}=0} = 3$$

since both the partial derivatives are positive, the current solution can be improved. As

$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2}$ gives the most positive value, x_2 will

enter the basis.

Now, to determine the leaving basic variable, we compute the ratios:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \left\{ \frac{\alpha_{ho}}{|\alpha_{hk}|}, \frac{\gamma_{ko}}{\gamma_{kk}} \right\} &= \min \left\{ \frac{\alpha_{30}}{|\alpha_{32}|}, \frac{\gamma_{20}}{|\alpha_{22}|} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \frac{4}{|-2|}, \frac{3}{0} \right\} = 2 \end{aligned}$$

since the minimum occurs for $\frac{\alpha_{30}}{|\alpha_{32}|}$, s will

leave the basis and it was introduced by [10]. Thus expressing the new basic variable, x_2 as well as the objective function f

in terms of the new non-basic variables (x_1 and s) we have:

$$x_2 = 2 - \frac{x_1}{2} - \frac{s}{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } f &= 2x_1 + 3 \left(2 - \frac{x_1}{2} - \frac{s}{2} \right) - x_1^2 \\ &= 6 + \frac{x_1}{2} - \frac{3}{2}s - x_1^2 \end{aligned}$$

we, again, evaluate the partial derivatives of f w. r. to the non-basic variables:

$$\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1}\right)_{x_{NB}=0} = \left(\frac{1}{2} - 2x_1\right)_{x_1=0} = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial s}\right)_{x_{NB}=0} = -\frac{3}{2}.$$

since the partial derivatives are not all negative, the current solution is not optimal, clearly, x_1 will enter the basis.

For the next Criterion, we compute the ratios

$$\min \left\{ \frac{\alpha_{20}}{|\alpha_{21}|}, \frac{\gamma_{10}}{|\gamma_{11}|} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{2}{|-1/2|}, \frac{1/2}{|-2|} \right\} = \frac{3}{4}.$$

since the minimum of these ratios correspond to $\frac{|\gamma_{10}|}{|\gamma_{11}|}$, non-basic variables can be

removed. Thus we introduce a free variable, u_1 (unrestricted), as an additional non-basic variable, defined by

$$u_1 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2} - 2x_1 \right) = \frac{1}{4} - x_1$$

Note that now the basis has two basic variables x_2 and x_1 (just entered). That is, we have

$$x_{NB} = (s, u_1) \text{ and } x_B = (x_1, x_2)$$

Expressing the basic x_B in terms of non-basic

$$x_{NB}, \text{ we have, } x_1 = \frac{1}{4} - u_1$$

$$\text{and } x_2 = \frac{1}{2}(4 - x_1 - x_3) = \frac{15}{8} + \frac{1}{2}u_1 - \frac{1}{2}s.$$

The objective function, expressing in terms of x_{NB} is,

$$\begin{aligned} f &= 2 \left(\frac{1}{4} - u_1 \right) + 3 \left(\frac{15}{8} + \frac{1}{2}u_1 - \frac{1}{2}s \right) - \left(\frac{1}{4} - u_1 \right)^2 \\ &= \frac{97}{16} - \frac{3}{2}s - u_1^2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Now, } \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial s}\right)_{x_{NB}=0, u=0} = -\frac{3}{2}; \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial u_1}\right)_{x_{NB}=0, u=0} = -2u_1 = 0$$

since $\frac{\partial f}{\partial u_1} \leq 0$ for all x_j in x_{NB} and $\frac{\partial f}{\partial u} = 0$,

the current solution is optimal. Hence the optimal basic feasible solution to the given problem is:

$$x_1 = \frac{1}{4}, \quad x_2 = \frac{15}{8}, \quad Z^* = \frac{97}{16}$$

Let us solve the given problem by [3] using Wolfe's algorithm

$$\text{Max } Z = 2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2$$

subject to the constraints

$$x_1 + 2x_2 \leq 4$$

$$x_1, x_2 \geq 0$$

First we convert the inequality constraints to equality by introducing slack variables $s \geq 0$

$$x_1 + 2x_2 + s = 4 \tag{18}$$

Therefore, the Lagrangian function of the problem is

$$L(x, \lambda) \equiv 2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2 + \lambda(4 - x_1 - 2x_2)$$

$$\text{Here } D = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, A = (1 \ 2), A^T = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 2 \\ 3 \end{pmatrix}, b = (4)$$

We know by Wolfe's algorithm:

$$2DX - A^T \lambda + V = -C$$

$$\Rightarrow 2 \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \end{pmatrix} \lambda + \begin{pmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -2 \\ -3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\Rightarrow -2x_1 - \lambda + v_1 = -2$$

$$-2\lambda + v_2 = -3$$

$$\Rightarrow 2x_1 + \lambda - v_1 = 2 \tag{19}$$

$$2\lambda - v_2 = 3 \tag{20}$$

Introducing two artificial variables a_1 and a_2 in equations (4. 5) and (4. 6), we get

$$2x_1 + \lambda - v_1 + a_1 = 2 \tag{21}$$

$$2\lambda - v_2 + a_2 = 3 \tag{22}$$

The quadratic programming problem is equivalent to

$$\text{Min } Z = a_1 + a_2$$

$$\text{i.e. } \text{Max}(-Z) = -a_1 - a_2$$

subject to the constraints

$$x_1 + 2x_2 + s = 4$$

$$2x_1 + \lambda - v_1 + a_1 = 2$$

$$2\lambda - v_2 + a_2 = 3$$

$$x_1, x_2, \lambda, v_1, v_2, s, a_1, a_2 \geq 0$$

$$\text{with } x_1 v_1 = 0, x_2 v_2 = 0, \lambda s = 0$$

The solution of the problem can be shown in the following modified simplex tableau: It was Introduced by [10]. Here we get three constraints equations with eight unknown.

So, for basic solution of the system always three variables will take non-zero values and others are zero. We will find out non zero values for x_1, x_2 & λ or s In our case initial basic solution is $a_1 = 2, a_2 = 3, s = 4 \Rightarrow z = 0$. Our next goal is to improve the value of Z. In tableau -1, we put constraints system as:

Table-1 Constraints system

x_1	x_2	λ	v_1	v_2	s	a_1	a_2	c
1	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	4
2	0	1	-1	0	0	1	0	2
0	0	2	0	-1	0	0	1	3

Now taking x_1 as leading variables. Then we get min (4/1, 2/2) is 2/2. So, second element of the 1st column is the pivotal element and the corresponding column is the pivotal column. So, x_1 enters in basis. Reducing the pivotal element to unity by dividing all elements of the pivotal row by 2, we get the table 2.

Table-2 Reducing first pivotal element to unity.

x_1	x_2	λ	v_1	v_2	s	a_1	a_2	c
1	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	4
1	0	1/2	-1/2	0	0	1/2	0	1
0	0	2	0	-1	0	0	1	3

Reducing zero all elements of the pivotal column except pivotal one, we get the table 3

Table-3 Reducing zero all elements of 1st pivotal column except pivotal one.

x_1	x_2	λ	v_1	v_2	s	a_1	a_2	c
0	2	-1/2	1/2	0	1	-1/2	0	3
1	0	1/2	-1/2	0	0	1/2	0	1
0	0	2	0	-1	0	0	1	3

Now taking x_2 as our next leading variable. Then we get 1st element of the second column is our next pivotal element. Reducing it to unity by dividing all elements of the pivotal now by 2 and next taking λ as our next leading variable. Then we get min $\left\{ \frac{1}{1/2}, \frac{3}{2} \right\}$ is $\frac{3}{2}$. So, 2 is our next pivotal

element. Reducing the pivotal element to unity, we get, the tableau-5.

Table-4 Reducing 3rd pivotal element to unity.

x_1	x_2	λ	v_1	v_2	s	a_1	a_2	c
0	1	-1/4	1/4	0	1/2	-1/4	0	3/2
1	0	1/2	-1/2	0	0	1/2	0	1
0	0	1	0	-1/2	0	0	1/2	3/2

Making zero all elements of the pivotal column except pivotal one, we get the table 5.

Table-5 Optimal solution

x_1	x_2	λ	v_1	v_2	s	a_1	a_2	c
0	1	0	1/4	-1/8	1/2	-1/4	1/8	15/8
1	0	0	-1/2	1/4	0	0	-1/4	1/4
0	0	1	0	-1/2	0	0	1/2	3/2

From T-5 we obtain the optimal solution as

$$x_1 = \frac{1}{4}, x_2 = \frac{15}{8}, \lambda = \frac{3}{2}.$$

Thus for the optimal solution for the given QP problem is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max } Z &= 2x_1 + 3x_2 - x_1^2 \\ &= 2 \cdot \frac{1}{4} + 3 \cdot \frac{15}{8} - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2 \\ &= \frac{97}{16} \quad \text{at } (x_1^*, x_2^*) = \left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{15}{8}\right). \end{aligned}$$

which is same as we obtain by Kuhn-Tucker condition method. For all kinds of non-linear programming problem, we can show that the optimal solution by Kuhn-tucker condition is same as any other method we considered. Therefore the solution obtained by graphical solution method, Kuhn-Tucker conditions and Wolfe's method are same.

5 Conclusion

To obtain an optimal solution to the non-linear programming problem, we observe that Kuhn-Tucker conditions are more useful than any other methods of solving NLP problem. Because in a NLP problem particular problems are solve by particular method. There is no universalism in the methods of solving NLP problem. But we have shown that by Kuhn-Tucker conditions all kinds of NLP problems can be solved. The NLP problem involving two variables can easily solve by graphical solution method, but the

problem involving more variables cannot solve by graphical solution method. Besides, for all NLP problems, graphical solution method do not gives always-optimal solution. Only quadratic programming problems can solve by Wolfe's method.

Therefore, from the above discussion, we can say that kuhn-Tucker conditions are the best method for solving only NLP problem.

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